

The administrative disciplinary proceedings and the fundamental right to due process of law: an analysis of the (non)mandatory nature of technical defense based on the principles of contradictory and full legal defense

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Abstract: This paper analyzes the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD) within the Brazilian Rule of Law, focusing on the constitutional right to be heard and to full legal defense. It investigates the extent to which due process of law is effectively observed within Public Administration. The research is based on the hypothesis that the absence of mandatory qualified legal counsel, as provided for in Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Brazilian Federal Supreme Court, compromises the full realization of these fundamental rights in the PAD. The study discusses fundamental rights and guarantees as limits on state power and as foundations for the legitimacy of administrative decisions, emphasizing the importance of professional legal representation. The hypothetical-deductive method is employed, based on documentary, bibliographic, and doctrinal research, as well as normative analysis. The results indicate that the PAD, as an instrument of the State's sanctioning power, must ensure administrative practices that uphold the right to be heard and full legal defense, thereby reinforcing legality and impartiality within Public Administration.

Keywords: Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding; Rule of Law; Due Process of Law; Right to Be Heard; Full Legal Defense; Qualified Legal Counsel.

Preliminary Remarks

The consolidation of the Rule of Law in Brazil, enshrined in the 1988 Federal Constitution, established a new paradigm for limiting state power, guided by the centrality of fundamental rights and the subordination of administrative activities to constitutional principles such as legality, the right to be heard, full legal defense, and due process of law. Within this context, the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD) acquires special legal and institutional relevance, as it constitutes a mechanism through which the State exercises its

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sanctioning power over public agents, with direct repercussions on individual rights, including those of a fundamental nature.

Within this legal-constitutional framework, the general objective of this research is to analyze the effectiveness of the guarantees of the right to be heard, full legal defense, and due process of law within the scope of the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding, in light of the Rule of Law and the requirements for the legitimacy of administrative decisions. Specifically, the study aims to: (i) examine the constitutional foundations of due process of law and its application to sanctioning administrative procedures; (ii) discuss the compatibility of Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Brazilian Federal Supreme Court with the constitutional model of a fair and effective procedure; (iii) reflect on the need for qualified legal counsel in the PAD; and (iv) propose a guarantee-based reinterpretation of the disciplinary procedure in light of the strengthening of procedural safeguards.

The central research question guiding this study is: to what extent is the fundamental right to due process of law effectively observed in the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding within Brazilian Public Administration, especially considering the non-mandatory nature of legal representation by an attorney? This issue becomes even more relevant when it is recognized that the PAD, although not part of the formal jurisdiction of the Judiciary, has a punitive nature and may result in serious consequences for the legal status of civil servants, such as warnings, suspensions, and even dismissals, which requires strict compliance with the principles of a fair proceeding.

The research is based on the hypothesis that waiving mandatory legal counsel, as established in Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme Court, undermines the realization of the constitutional guarantees of the right to be heard and full legal defense, weakening the mechanisms of control over state power and the legitimacy of the sanctioning administrative process. It is assumed that, even within the sphere of Public Administration, punitive procedures must ensure that the accused has both formal and substantive means to present a defense, which implies, in certain contexts, the necessity of legal assistance by a qualified professional.

To investigate this hypothesis, the study adopts the hypothetical-deductive method, which is suitable for theoretical and normative legal research. This method begins with the formulation of an interpretive hypothesis - in this case, the incompatibility between the waiver of legal counsel and the requirements of due process of law - and seeks to test it through a critical analysis of constitutional foundations, legal texts, administrative documents, and judicial decisions. The reasoning is developed through the deduction of legal consequences, connecting constitutional norms and principles with the institutional practice of the PAD.

As for the methodological procedures, the research has a qualitative character, with an emphasis on theoretical and dogmatic investigation. The following techniques are used: (i) bibliographic research, involving the reading and analysis of national and international doctrinal works on administrative procedure, fundamental guarantees, and legal representation; (ii) documentary research, comprising the examination of laws, regulations, ordinances, and other normative acts governing the PAD within the Brazilian legal system; (iii) jurisprudential analysis, with special attention to the content and scope of Binding Precedent No. 5 and related decisions of the Brazilian Federal Supreme Court; and (iv) systematic-normative analysis, aimed at interpreting the constitutional principles applicable to the disciplinary administrative procedure in light of the guarantee-based model of the State.

The results achieved throughout the research demonstrate that the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD), due to its sanctioning nature and the effects it produces on the fundamental rights of public servants, must be conducted in strict observance of the constitutional principles of due process of law, the right to be heard, and full legal defense,

under penalty of violating the legality and legitimacy of administrative decisions. It was found that, although the Federal Supreme Court's consolidated jurisprudence, through Binding Precedent No. 5, affirms the non-requirement of mandatory legal representation in the PAD, such an interpretation proves to be limited and insufficient in light of the increasing complexity of administrative procedures and the technical asymmetry between Public Administration and the accused.

The doctrinal analysis revealed that the absence of proper legal assistance may impair the effective exercise of the right to defense, especially in cases involving technical evidence, complex charges, or serious consequences such as dismissal from public service. In such contexts, qualified legal counsel does not represent a privilege or an excess of guarantees, but rather a necessary condition for the full exercise of substantive due process - one that goes beyond mere awareness of procedural acts and entails the real opportunity to influence the content of decisions.

It was also observed that the binding precedent, by abstractly standardizing the non-requirement of an attorney, disregards the principles of reasonableness and proportionality, which demand a contextual and concrete assessment of the need for legal representation in each case. Such generalization compromises the effectiveness of the administrative sanctioning process as a legitimate and transparent means of overseeing the conduct of public agents, potentially resulting in legal uncertainty and the violation of constitutional guarantees.

The research further demonstrated that, from the perspective of the guarantee-based model of the Rule of Law, the PAD must be interpreted in a manner consistent with the requirements of a fair and effective procedure. This implies recognizing that legal representation, although not mandatory in all cases, must be considered indispensable whenever the complexity of the matter or the severity of the sanction justifies its presence. In such cases, it is the duty of the Public Administration to ensure actual conditions for its exercise, including the provision of a public defender or free legal aid, when necessary.

Finally, it was concluded that the reinterpretation of Binding Precedent No. 5, in light of contemporary constitutional principles and the doctrine of substantive due process, is a necessary measure for the realization of fundamental guarantees within the scope of the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD). Such reinterpretation does not entail the repeal of the precedent, but rather its restrictive and balanced application, in accordance with the 1988 Federal Constitution and the values that underpin a guarantee-based administrative procedure. Thus, the results indicate the urgency of a critical reassessment of current administrative practices, with a view to implementing normative and institutional measures that ensure the effectiveness of qualified legal counsel in the PAD as a means of protecting the dignity of public servants, the legality of administrative acts, and the legitimacy of State actions.

The structure of this paper is organized into three main sections, in addition to these preliminary remarks and the final considerations. Section 2, entitled *The Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding in the Brazilian Rule of Law*, examines the role of the PAD in the context of the Rule of Law, with emphasis on the centrality of fundamental rights as structuring elements of administrative action. Section 3, *The Fundamental Right to Due Process of Law in the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding*, deepens the analysis of the normative content and guarantee-based dimension of due process of law, highlighting the rights to be heard and to full legal defense as essential principles for the legitimacy of administrative sanctions. Section 4, *Qualified Legal Counsel in the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding as an Expression of the Right to Be Heard and Full Legal Defense*, presents a critical approach to the non-mandatory nature of legal representation in the PAD, based on the jurisprudence of the Federal Supreme Court, particularly Binding Precedent No. 5, confronting this understanding with the constitutional parameters of a fair and effective procedure.

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2. The Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding in the Brazilian Rule of Law

Throughout the historical evolution of the Constitutional State, after the overcoming of the liberal and social models, the Rule of Law was consolidated as a result of the combination between the legitimacy of power exercised by the people and the centrality of fundamental rights and guarantees. These rights, whether explicitly stated or implied in the Constitution, function as limits to state power, preventing it from operating in an authoritarian or arbitrary manner. This model not only formalizes the union between the rule of law and democracy, but also transcends them.

As José Afonso da Silva emphasizes, “the democratic state under the rule of law reconciles the democratic state and the rule of law, but it does not merely consist of the formal combination of the elements of these two types of state. It truly reveals a new concept that incorporates the principles of those two models, but goes beyond them by adding a revolutionary component of transformation of the *status quo*³.”

The foundation of the Rule of Law as we understand it today is rooted in the contractualism of Jean-Jacques Rousseau, who, by adding the element of sovereignty to the social contract proposed by Locke, affirmed that the renunciation of certain individual liberties under the guardianship of a third party - as the arbiter of conflicts embodied in the figure of the State - does not imply subjugation to the will of that State, but rather submission to the general will⁴.

Bruna Schlindwein Zeni and Tânia Regina Silva Reckziegel write that “for Rousseau, what matters is the prominence of the public interest within the Social Contract, which, in turn, reaffirms liberty and democracy, as well as popular sovereignty. These arise from the fact that what dictates the rule to the sovereign is the general will, whose expression is found in the law, and from the understanding that everyone governs for everyone, through a sovereign body called the State, and thus, no one limits anyone else’s freedom⁵.”

Ronaldo Brêtas de Carvalho Dias teaches that democracy, as a source of legitimization of power, is configured as a legal principle with a formal and organic nature, constituting a central element of the constitutional order. Brêtas defines the Rule of Law as a principle with both material and procedural dimensions: on the one hand, it structures the exercise of state power, and on the other, it recognizes fundamental rights and ensures judicial control over the legality of state actions. Furthermore, it guarantees civil servants the right of access to the judiciary. According to the author, the Rule of Law represents the synthesis of the principles of democracy and the legal state, expressed in a constitutional normative harmonization, in which power is legitimized by the popular will but finds its limits in the protection of fundamental rights. The modern State legitimizes its power based on popular participation and, at the same time, is structured around the protection and realization of fundamental rights, which guide the drafting, interpretation, and application of all norms within the legal system⁶.

³ Silva, José Afonso da. *The Democratic Rule of Law*. *Administrative Law Review*, vol. 173, pp. 15-16, 1988. Available at: <http://periodicos.fgv.br/rda/article/download/45920/44126>. Accessed: April 29, 2025.

⁴ Rousseau, Jean-Jacques. *The Social Contract*. São Paulo: Abril S.A. Cultural, 1973.

⁵ Zeni, Bruna Schlindwein; Reckziegel, Tânia Regina Silva. *Social Contract, Rule of Law, and Popular Participation*. In: *Proceedings of the XVIII National Congress of CONPEDI*, São Paulo, 2009, p. 3. Available at: http://www.publicadireito.com.br/conpedi/manuel/arquivos/anais/sao_paulo/2834.pdf. Accessed: April 21, 2025.

⁶ Bretas, Ronaldo de Carvalho Dias. *Constitutional Procedure and the Rule of Law*. Belo Horizonte: Del Rey, 2022, p. 69.

The Constitution is the foundation of the Rule of Law. As José Joaquim Gomes Canotilho⁷ affirms, the Constitutional State must be organized as a Rule of Law, that is, a system of power legitimized by the people. Within this structure, the exercise of power must respect principles and fundamental rights. One may therefore consider that, in the Rule of Law, constitutional principles are centrally oriented toward the affirmation of fundamental rights, which are regarded as guiding elements of the legal order.

Ronaldo Brêtas de Carvalho Dias⁸ also states that the recognition of fundamental rights in the Constitution and in contemporary infraconstitutional norms forms a solid system of protection against abuse and arbitrariness by the State. This system reaffirms that all state actions must be bound to the principles of the Rule of Law, which is presented as a State of Fundamental Rights. The author notes that, despite the distinctions of the Rule of Law both converge in the valorization of individual freedom, which reveals that fundamental rights are simultaneously the purpose and the substance of the State. In this context, it is brought to light that constitutional principles, as binding legal norms, are an integral part of the legal system and guide the exercise of jurisdiction⁹.

It is observed that the provisions of the Constitution not only structure the State but also function as elements for the creation, interpretation, integration, and application of laws. Thus, the Rule of Law, understood as a Constitutional State of Rights, finds its justification in the guarantee of a legal regime oriented toward the protection of fundamental rights. This context invites reflection on the importance of constitutional procedure in upholding the legal principles.

In Brazil, the 1988 Federal Constitution marks a significant moment in the institutional strengthening of the Brazilian State. By establishing the primacy of fundamental rights and expanding the instruments of popular participation, it affirms itself as a concrete expression of the Rule of Law and consolidates itself as an inclusive democratic model, oriented toward the protection of individual and collective rights, as well as the promotion of citizenship and the respect for human dignity. This conception is especially reflected in Article 1, which enshrines democracy as a fundamental principle of the Brazilian State.

Within this context, the 1988 Federal Constitution may be understood through the lens of the Directive Constitution concept, since, as taught by Ricardo Quartim de Moraes¹⁰, it guides both the drafting of laws and the conduct of the State. The author asserts that the 1988 Constitution not only imposes restrictions on the content of laws but also establishes directives that must be actively followed (positive guidelines).

This set of procedural guarantees and fundamental rights, internalized in the constitutional text and guiding state action, has had repercussions in Administrative Disciplinary Law, understood as the body of rules and standards governing the procedure aimed at resolving disputes arising from the failure of those who exercise administrative activity to comply with legal obligations.

⁷ Canotilho, José Joaquim Gomes. *Rule of Law*. Lisbon, Portugal: Gradiva, 1999, p. 10. Available at: <http://www.academia.edu/download/33341061/jjgcoedd.pdf>. Accessed: April 20, 2025.

⁸ Bretas, Ronaldo de Carvalho Dias. *Constitutional Procedure and the Rule of Law*. 2022, p. 87.

⁹ Bretas, Ronaldo de Carvalho Dias. *Constitutional Procedure and the Rule of Law*. 2022, pp. 147-204.

¹⁰ Moraes, Ricardo Quartim de. *The Historical Evolution from the Liberal State to the Rule of Law and Its Relationship with Directive Constitutionalism*. Legislative Information Review, vol. 51, no. 204, 2014, p. 279. Available at: http://www12.senado.leg.br/ril/edicoes/51/204/ril_v51_n204_p269. Accessed: April 20, 2025.

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Giovani Orso Borile and Marianita Filippon¹¹ note that, in such cases, an Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD) will be initiated, made possible by the Disciplinary Power inherent to Administrative Law. According to the authors, the PAD serves not only to punish but also to improve and train civil servants, ensuring compliance with regulations and the quality of services provided to the population.

The definition of the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding can be clearly understood in the text of Law No. 8,112/1990¹², which governs the legal regime of federal public servants within the Union, autonomous agencies, and federal public foundations. The article 148 of the law expressly states: “The disciplinary proceeding is the instrument intended to determine the responsibility of a public servant for an infraction committed in the exercise of their duties, or one that is related to the duties of the position they hold.”

The Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding was expressly referenced in the 1988 Federal Constitution under Article 5, item LV, and Article 41, § 1, items II and III. It also finds implicit foundation in the set of fundamental rights, particularly in Article 1, caput and item III; Article 5, item LIV; and Article 37¹³. In this regard, Romeu Felipe Bacellar Filho and Daniel Wunder Hachem point out that “administrative procedure entered Brazilian constitutional texts through the establishment of a procedural regime regulating the dismissal of public servants,” which first appeared in the Constitutions of 1934, 1937, and 1967, as well as in Constitutional Amendment No. 1/1969. According to the authors, all constitutional references prior to 1988 concerned only the requirement of an administrative process for cases involving dismissal from public service. The 1988 Constitution was innovative in expressly providing, in Article 5, item LV, the guarantee of the right to be heard and full legal defense for litigants in administrative procedures¹⁴.

Through the enshrinement of the principles of the Rule of Law in the 1988 Federal Constitution - especially regarding due process of law and, consequently, the principles of legality, full legal defense, the right to be heard, efficiency, and morality - the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding came to have a clear constitutional foundation. It affirmed the guarantee that the conduct of Public Administration must be subject to the rights and fundamental guarantees of individuals, including those who perform administrative functions.

3. The Fundamental Right to Due Process of Law in the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding

The Constitutional Procedural System, enshrined in the 1988 Federal Constitution¹⁵, constitutes the normative expression of the democratic order and the primary means for realizing fundamental rights and guarantees in both judicial and administrative proceedings. It

¹¹ Borile, Giovani Orso; Filippon, Marianita. *Brazilian Administrative Disciplinary Procedure. Cadernos de Direito Actual*, no. 9, 2018, p. 384. Available at: <http://www.cadernosdedereitoactual.es/index.php/cadernos/article/view/319>. Accessed: July 2, 2025.

¹² Brazil. Law No. 8,112 of December 11, 1990. Establishes the legal regime for federal civil servants of the Union, autonomous agencies, and federal public foundations. *Official Gazette of the Union: Section 1*, Brasília, DF, Dec. 12, 1990. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/l8112cons.htm. Accessed: July 2, 2025.

¹³ Brazil. [Constitution (1988)]. *Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988*. Brasília, DF: Presidency of the Republic, [2016]. *Official Gazette of the Union*, Brasília, DF. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm. Accessed: March 14, 2025.

¹⁴ Bacellar Filho, Romeu Felipe; Hachem, Daniel Wunder. *The Need for Legal Counsel in the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding and the Unconstitutionality of Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme Court. A&C – Administrative & Constitutional Law Review*, 2010, p. 32. Available at: <http://revistaaec.com/index.php/revistaaec/article/view/288/141>. Accessed: May 6, 2025.

¹⁵ Brazil. [Constitution (1988)]. *Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988*. Brasília, DF: Presidency of the Republic, [2016]. *Official Gazette of the Union*, Brasília, DF. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm. Accessed: March 14, 2025.

is a set of norms, principles, and values that impose upon State action - whether by the Judiciary or by the Public Administration - the duty to observe the constitutional parameters of legality, the right to be heard, full legal defense, due process of law, reasoned decisions, proportionality, and reasonableness. This constitutionalized procedural structure not only binds the exercise of jurisdictional functions but also conditions the validity and effectiveness of administrative sanctioning acts, such as the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD).

José Joaquim Gomes Canotilho¹⁶, when addressing the normative force of fundamental rights, argues that these rights function as “*directive dimensions*” of the Constitution - that is, they guide not only the interpretation of infra-constitutional norms but also the structural organization of the State and its public institutions. In this sense, fundamental rights are not limited to ensuring individual liberties, but serve as normative pillars that shape State decision-making procedures, functioning as conditions for validity and criteria for the legitimacy of administrative acts. Thus, the Constitutional Procedural System imposes upon Public Administration the obligation to structure its procedures - including disciplinary proceedings - in accordance with guarantee-based principles, ensuring individuals real and substantive conditions for the exercise of the right to be heard and full legal defense, under penalty of nullity and unconstitutionality of the decisions adopted.

Given their importance, it is expected that fundamental rights should not face barriers to their concrete implementation, since their primary purpose is precisely to transform the human values enshrined in the Constitution into reality. In this context, constitutional rights and guarantees - as mechanisms for protecting fundamental rights - require coherent and coordinated action between rules and principles in order to ensure their validity, legal effectiveness, and, above all, their practical enforceability.

As José Afonso da Silva¹⁷ observes, effectiveness is the dimension in which a constitutional norm transcends mere formal existence and the production of legal effects, becoming operative in social reality. It refers to the degree to which the objectives of the norm are fulfilled, which presupposes not only its validity and legal effectiveness but also its actual application and capacity to influence social and institutional behavior. According to the author, a norm may be valid and effective yet lack effectiveness if its commands are not observed in practice - whether due to the absence of political will, institutional inertia, or structural barriers. This distinction is crucial in the context of the administrative disciplinary process, where the constitutional guarantee of the right to be heard and full legal defense, although legally effective, often fails to achieve full effectiveness, especially in situations involving technical imbalance between the parties or the absence of qualified legal counsel. Therefore, the effectiveness of constitutional guarantees in the PAD cannot be assessed solely on the basis of their legal provision but must be evaluated through the concrete analysis of their application - failing which, the constitutional promises risk being hollowed out, and the Rule of Law weakened.

At this point, Gabriela Oliveira Freitas¹⁸ draws attention to the fact that the protection of fundamental rights and their practical realization have come to occupy a central place within the Rule of Law. As these guarantees are not confined to the abstract plane of the constitutional text but require effective instruments for their enforcement, it becomes inevitable that legal proceedings - both judicial and administrative - be understood as privileged means for the realization of fundamental rights. As the author rightly emphasizes, “constitutional guarantees become highly relevant in the study of procedural law, considering that many of

¹⁶ Canotilho, José Joaquim Gomes. Das constituições dos direitos. *Revista ConJur*, 28 out. 2022. Disponível em: <http://www.conjur.com.br>. Acesso em: 20 abr. 2025.

¹⁷ Silva, José Afonso da. *Applicability of Constitutional Norms*. São Paulo: Malheiros Publisher, 1999.

¹⁸ Freitas, Gabriela Oliveira. *The Constitutional Process as a Guarantee of Fundamental Rights in the Rule of Law*. *Lex Humana* (ISSN 2175-0947), vol. 5, no. 1, 2013, p. 58. Available at: <http://seer.ucp.br/seer/index.php/LexHumana/article/view/298>. Accessed: April 20, 2025.

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these guarantees, although provided for in the constitutional text, have a procedural nature [...]”. This means, in practice, that it is no longer possible to conceive of procedural law as dissociated from the Constitution, since it is the space in which such rights must be concretely manifested. In the case of the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding, this understanding acquires even greater relevance, given that it is a punitive procedure often marked by imbalances between the Administration and the accused public servant. Thus, when one refers to the right to be heard, full legal defense, or due process of law, what is at stake is not merely the formal structure of the proceeding, but the very realization of a model of State committed to limiting power and protecting the dignity of the individual in the face of State authority.

The provision of due process of law in Article 5, item LIV, of the 1988 Federal Constitution¹⁹ establishes an essential barrier against State arbitrariness: no one shall be deprived of liberty or property without a proceeding that observes minimum standards of justice. Although it is a clause frequently invoked in legal debates, its content demands a more rigorous and less superficial interpretation. Humberto Ávila²⁰ distinguishes two dimensions of this principle: one procedural - referring to compliance with formal stages, such as the right to be heard and full legal defense - and another substantive, focused on controlling the reasonableness and proportionality of State decisions. This distinction is relevant because it reveals that a proceeding may be formally correct yet materially unjust. Legitimacy, therefore, does not derive solely from procedural compliance but from conformity with substantive values of justice, especially when the State exercises its punitive power over individuals. When applied to the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding, this understanding requires a more demanding interpretation of the principle, in which adequate procedural structure must be accompanied by substantive fairness. That is, the procedure must not only respect formal steps but also ensure balance, impartiality, and protection against disproportionate sanctions. This integrative view contributes to reinforcing the understanding that due process of law, in its full scope, is an indispensable condition for ensuring that the exercise of the State’s sanctioning power does not compromise the foundations of the Rule of Law.

Rubens Alexandre Elias Calixto²¹ identifies the safeguarding of fundamental rights as one of the essential functions of due process of law. On this point, the author writes: “It is possible to identify, in the complexity of due process of law, certain inherent functions. One of them is to serve as a support for the affirmation of fundamental rights in general, particularly in cases where the recognition of these rights depends on a profound interpretive activity by administrative and judicial bodies. This affirmative role stems from the ethical and political component of due process of law and from its axiological essence, which is closely related to the notion of fairness”.

It is observed that due process of law presents itself simultaneously as both a guarantee and a guarantor. Moreover, this function is especially evident when the recognition of rights requires intensive interpretive activity by administrative and judicial bodies. From this perspective, due process of law acquires an ethical and political dimension, closely linked to the notion of fairness. It is not merely about ensuring a procedural rite, but about guaranteeing decisions grounded in constitutional values, reinforcing the centrality of fundamental rights within the Rule of Law.

¹⁹ Brazil. [Constitution (1988)]. *Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988*. Brasília, DF: Presidency of the Republic, [2016]. *Official Gazette of the Union*, Brasília, DF. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm. Accessed: March 14, 2025.

²⁰ Ávila, Humberto. *What Is “Due Process of Law”*. In: *Revista de Processo*, 2008, p. 51. Available at: http://env1.cursopopulardefensoria.com.br/pluginfile.php/4811/mod_resource/content/1/avila-humberto-o-que-e-devido-processo-legal.pdf. Accessed: April 21, 2025.

²¹ Calixto, Rubens Alexandre Elias. *Due Process of Law*. *Electronic Journal of the Faculty of Law of Franca*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2016, pp. 244-245. Available at: <http://revista.direitofranca.br/index.php/refdf/article/view/344>. Accessed: April 21, 2025.

In this regard, Bernardo Silva de Seixas and Roberta Kelly Silva Souza²² assert that “the principle of due process of law is the foundation upon which all other principles and rules rest. From it flow all procedural consequences, which aim to guarantee litigants the right to a process with adversarial participation and full legal defense, in which the parties are treated equally, under a pre-existing law, by the impartial and independent authority of a natural judge who will render a fair judgment.” In this scenario, the authors further state that “it is possible to affirm that the principle of due process of law is an indispensable means for the realization of the individual’s fundamental rights in the procedural sphere, representing, beyond the idea of a procedure, the appropriate instrumental means by which the State may, through the exercise of jurisdiction, give each person what is rightfully theirs”.

It is also important to note that Guilherme César Pinheiro²³ distinguishes, within procedural dynamics, the legal-technical content of the right to be heard and full legal defense. According to the author, the normative content of the principle of the right to be heard is expressed through the binomials of notice and participation, action and reaction, thus “requiring that the parties be given the opportunity to express their views on all matters relevant to the resolution of the case - whether factual or legal, material or procedural, ex officio or not, evidentiary or related to binding precedents, case law, or prevailing jurisprudence.”

Regarding the fundamental right to full legal defense, the author emphasizes that this legal principle, due to its dense content, “is not limited to submitting a response to the claim made by the plaintiff but unfolds throughout all stages of the proceeding under a regime of adversarial participation between the parties.” He further affirms that it “requires the creation of technical means (legal instruments) and appropriate procedural space-time (deadlines) to ensure that the defense is broad and effective, securing the right of the parties to argue and critically interpret legal texts, thereby conferring legitimacy upon the legal order.” It also guarantees “the right of the parties to prove, by lawful means, the arguments advanced in the proceedings and to appeal against the decisions rendered therein,” and it equally “requires that the parties be assisted by legal counsel, while also guaranteeing the right to self-representation”.²⁴

In this dialogue among legal sources concerning the principles of adversarial proceedings and full defense, José dos Santos Carvalho Filho²⁵ emphasizes that holding public agents accountable within the scope of Public Administration necessarily requires the initiation of a formal administrative proceeding, in which the civil servant is guaranteed not only the right to full defense and adversarial proceedings, but also broad evidentiary means capable of enabling the effective ascertainment of the truth. For the author, the pursuit of efficiency in the investigation of misconduct cannot occur at the expense of constitutional safeguards, under penalty of invalidating the entire procedure.

²² Seixas, Bernardo Silva de; Souza, Roberta Kelly Silva. The Importance of the Constitutional Principle of Due Process of Law for Effective Access to Justice in Brazil. *Cadernos do Programa de Pós-Graduação em Direito - PPGDir./UFRGS*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2014, p. 244. Available at: <http://seer.ufrgs.br/ppgdir/article/view/44535>. Accessed: April 21, 2025.

²³ Pinheiro, Guilherme César. Theoretical Foundations and Technical Aspects of the Right to Full Defense. *Legislative Information Journal*, vol. 59, no. 233, 2022, p. 104. Available at: http://www12.senado.leg.br/ril/edicoes/59/233/ril_v59_n233_p99. Accessed: April 29, 2025.

²⁴ Pinheiro, Guilherme César. Theoretical foundations and technical aspects of the right to full defense. *Legislative Information Journal*, vol. 59, no. 233, 2022, p. 101. Available at: http://www12.senado.leg.br/ril/edicoes/59/233/ril_v59_n233_p99. Accessed on: April 29, 2025.

²⁵ Carvalho Filho, José dos Santos. *Manual of Administrative Law*. São Paulo: Atlas, 2015, p. 802. Available at: <http://morumbidireito.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/direito-administrativo-28c2aa-ed-2015-josc3a9-dos-santos-carvalho-filho.pdf>. Accessed on: April, 21, 2025.

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Lúcia Valle Figueiredo²⁶, in turn, complements this perspective by stating that any procedure with a sanctioning character or involving restriction of rights - even in cases where the Administration reviews its own acts - requires the mandatory presence of the guarantees of adversarial proceedings and full defense. According to the author, these principles are essential for the legitimacy of administrative acts, particularly in situations involving “accused” individuals, even if not in the strict criminal-legal sense. She further develops her argument by linking the application of due process of law - especially in its substantive dimension - to the very rationale of administrative function. It is this substantive and guarantee-based understanding of due process that ensures the protection of individual, collective, and diffuse rights, while also conferring rationality and fairness to State action.

Both authors, therefore, albeit through different paths, converge in defending that the legitimacy of sanctioning administrative procedures depends entirely on their structuring upon the foundations of due process of law, adversarial proceedings, and full legal defense, reaffirming the Public Administration’s commitment to the constitutional values of the Rule of Law. Such legitimacy does not stem solely from formal compliance with procedural steps, but from the actual opportunity granted to the affected party to influence the outcome of the proceeding by fully exercising their right to defense in the face of State action.

In this regard, adversarial proceedings must not be understood merely as the notification of procedural acts, but as a real opportunity for the party to present arguments and respond to the accusations made. Full legal defense, in turn, requires the use of all legally permitted means and remedies to protect the interests of the accused, including, when necessary, technical assistance provided by a qualified professional. The principle of Due process of law, in both its procedural and substantive dimensions, thus functions as a true material limit to the exercise of the State’s sanctioning power, preventing the administrative authority from acting in an arbitrary or disproportionate manner.

Authors such as Romeu Felipe Bacellar Filho, Daniel Wunder Hachem, Yduan May, and Mauricio da Cunha Savino Filó recognize that the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD), due to its sanctioning nature, requires full observance of the constitutional guarantees set forth in Article 5, item LV, of the 1988 Federal Constitution. According to Romeu Felipe Bacellar Filho and Daniel Wunder Hachem²⁷, the rights to adversarial proceedings and full legal defense unfold into concrete guarantees, such as the individualization of conduct, the right to be heard, to produce evidence, to receive a reasoned decision, and to be assisted by technical legal defense. These guarantees are indispensable for the protection of legally safeguarded interests such as honor, image, and labor, all constitutionally recognized.

In turn, Yduan May and Mauricio da Cunha Savino Filó²⁸ reinforce this perspective by characterizing the PAD as an internal punitive procedure whose consequences may have implications in the criminal sphere. They argue that the Public Administration must submit to the regime of fundamental guarantees, ensuring that due process of law, particularly in its substantive dimension, is effectively enforced. Thus, the legitimacy of the PAD requires more than formal legality - it demands a commitment to substantive justice.

²⁶ Figueiredo, Lúcia Valle. Rule of Law and Due Process of Law. *Administrative Law Review*, vol. 209, 1997, pp. 16-18. Available at: <http://periodicos.fgv.br/rda/article/view/47039>. Accessed: April, 20, 2025.

²⁷ Bacellar Filho, Romeu Felipe; Hachem, Daniel Wunder. The necessity of technical defense in the administrative disciplinary proceeding and the unconstitutionality of Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme Court. *Journal of Administrative and Constitutional Law*, 2010, pp. 35-55. Available at: <http://revistaec.com/index.php/revistaec/article/view/288/141>. Accessed on: May 6, 2025.

²⁸ May, Yduan; Filó, Mauricio da Cunha Savino. The principles of adversarial proceedings and full defense as historical instruments ensuring the effectiveness and legitimacy of the administrative disciplinary proceeding. *Journal of Fundamental Rights and Guarantees*, v. 16, n. 2, 2015, pp. 153-160. Available at: <http://dialnet.unirioja.es/descarga/articulo/5662366.pdf>. Accessed on: July 7, 2025.

As can be observed, the rights to adversarial proceedings and full defense are essential constitutional guarantees for the legitimacy of the Administrative Disciplinary Proceeding (PAD). They go beyond the mere formality of allowing the parties to speak; rather, they constitute indispensable safeguards, including the right to be heard, to produce evidence, to receive a reasoned decision, and, importantly, the right to qualified technical defense. The sanctioning character of the PAD, combined with the potential impact on fundamental rights such as honor, image, employment, and the very dignity of the civil servant, demands that the procedure adhere to a guarantee-based model, governed by legality, reasonableness, proportionality, and, above all, by the strict respect for adversarial proceedings and full legal defense. Disregarding these guarantees undermines not only the rights of the citizen but also the very legitimacy of State action.

4. Legal Counsel in Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings as an Expression of the Adversarial Principle and the Right to a Full Defense

The analysis of the constitutional principles of adversarial proceedings and full defense within Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings raises the issue of representation by legal counsel. Beatriz Iaczk and Ana Cláudia Finger²⁹ note that “Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings (PAD), in particular, have quite peculiar features due to the underlying substantive legal relationship, involving the exercise of the State’s sanctioning power, which requires a considerably more intense implementation of procedural guarantees for the accused - an issue that has traditionally led to debate over the mandatory nature of so-called legal counsel.”

According to Lúcia Valle Figueiredo³⁰, “whenever there is prejudice to the party, legal counsel becomes indispensable; only in the event of no actual prejudice may it be waived.” The author further argues that “in the absence of legal counsel - especially in disciplinary proceedings - there is, in most cases, no full legal defense, no truly effective defense, no defense where there is a genuine opportunity for adversarial proceedings and exhaustive evidentiary production.”

The mandatory presence of legal counsel in Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings had been a settled matter before the Superior Court of Justice (STJ), as reflected in Precedent No. 343³¹, which required the participation of legal counsel at all stages of the administrative sanctioning procedure. This Precedent from the STJ was aligned with Brazil’s constitutional framework, particularly with the fundamental right to full defense as enshrined in Article 5 of the 1988 Federal Constitution³².

Notwithstanding the settled position of the Superior Court of Justice (STJ), the Federal Supreme Court (STF) later adopted a divergent understanding. As explained by Romeu Felipe Bacellar Filho and Daniel Wunder Hachem³³, “in 2008, the Court ruled on Extraordinary Appeal

²⁹ Iaczk, Beatriz; Finger, Ana Cláudia. *Technical defense in administrative disciplinary proceedings: the principles of adversarial proceedings and full legal defense*. 2022. Available at: <http://www.academia.edu/download/97162621/65.pdf>. Accessed on: April 21, 2025.

³⁰ Figueiredo, Lúcia Valle. Rule of Law and Due Process of Law. *Administrative Law Review*, vol. 209, 1997, p. 17. Available at: <http://periodicos.fgv.br/rda/article/view/47039>. Accessed on: April 20, 2025.

³¹ Brazil. Superior Court of Justice. *Precedent No. 343*. Available at: http://www.stj.jus.br/docs_internet/revista/eletronica/stj-revista-sumulas-2012_29_capSumula343.pdf. Accessed on: July 29, 2025.

³² Brazil. [Constitution (1988)]. Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988. Brasília, DF: Office of the President of the Republic, [2016]. *Official Gazette of the Union*, Brasília, DF. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm. Accessed on: March 14, 2025.

³³ Bacellar Filho, Romeu Felipe; Hachem, Daniel Wunder. The Need for Legal Counsel in Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings and the Unconstitutionality of Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme

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No. 434.059-3/DF³⁴, concluding that legal counsel in administrative disciplinary proceedings is not mandatory, as it is not a constitutional requirement.” Subsequently, the Federal Supreme Court (STF) issued Binding Precedent No. 5³⁵, which explicitly stated that representation by legal counsel is not required in Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings.

This binding precedent currently produces legal effects within the Brazilian legal system and has guided the conduct of disciplinary procedures in public administration. What was once firmly established - namely, the constitutional guarantee of full legal defense embodied in the presence and participation of legal counsel throughout administrative disciplinary proceedings - has, despite the binding nature of the Federal Supreme Court’s precedent, become a controversial matter.

In this context, Ana Maria Pedreira³⁶ observes that the understanding adopted by the Federal Supreme Court in issuing Binding Precedent No. 5 was based on the existence of legal provisions that, in certain cases, allow individuals to act without the assistance of legal counsel - even in judicial proceedings, as is the case with habeas corpus petitions. However, according to the author, such reasoning disregards the fact that the presence of a lawyer becomes mandatory whenever the administrative decision may restrict individual rights or interests. She argues that the Federal Supreme Court’s position reflects an outdated conception whereby due process of law would be sufficiently guaranteed merely by access to the Jurisdiction - an understanding that is incompatible with the principles enshrined in the 1988 Federal Constitution, which affirms a substantive and rights-based model of procedural justice.

Following this line of reasoning, Romeu Felipe Bacellar Filho and Daniel Wunder Hachem³⁷ assert that the adoption of Binding Precedent No. 5 constitutes, *data venia*, a manifest unconstitutionality. According to the authors, the precedent undermines the doctrinal progress achieved in the field of constitutional guarantees applicable to disciplinary administrative proceedings, producing adverse effects throughout the Brazilian Public Administration. They emphasize that the precedent formally authorizes the violation of fundamental rights that had previously been recognized by national jurisprudence and materially contradicts the normative and axiological content of the 1988 Federal Constitution.

This scenario reveals a weakening in the effectiveness of fundamental rights, running counter to the constitutional mandate that imposes on the State a duty to promote and safeguard such rights. Rather than seeking to improve the procedural mechanisms that ensure their applicability, what is seen is a trend toward the undue flexibilization of due process guarantees in administrative disciplinary proceedings.

Court. *A&C - Journal of Administrative and Constitutional Law*, 2010, p. 36. Available at: <http://revistaaec.com/index.php/revistaaec/article/view/288/141>. Accessed on: May 6, 2025.

³⁴ Brazil. Federal Supreme Court. *Extraordinary Appeal No. 434.059-3/DF*. Rapporteur: Justice Gilmar Mendes. Brasília, DF, May 7, 2008. Available at: <http://redir.stf.jus.br/paginadorpub/paginador.jsp?docTP=AC&docID=547287>. Accessed on: July 29, 2025.

³⁵ Brazil. Federal Supreme Court. *Binding Precedent No. 5*. Available at: <http://noticias.stf.jus.br/postsnovicias/sumula-vinculante-no-5-stf-decide-que-nao-e-obrigatoria-defesa-elaborada-por-advogado-em-processo-administrativo-disciplinar/>. Accessed on: July 30, 2025.

³⁶ Pedreira, Ana Maria. *Contemporary Administrative Law*. Rio de Janeiro: Freitas Bastos, 2025. E-book. Available at: <http://plataforma.bvirtual.com.br>. Accessed on: July 2, 2025.

³⁷ Bacellar Filho, Romeu Felipe; Hachem, Daniel Wunder. The Need for Legal Counsel in Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings and the Unconstitutionality of Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme Court. *A&C - Journal of Administrative and Constitutional Law*, 2010, p. 36. Available at: <http://revistaaec.com/index.php/revistaaec/article/view/288/141>. Accessed on: May 6, 2025.

Within this framework, the absence of technical legal defense allows such proceedings to move forward without exhausting the legal means and resources that constitute a truly full legal defense - understood as the effective exercise of all lawful and legitimate instruments available to the accused. This omission compromises not only the procedural balance between the parties but also the very notion of substantive justice, given that full legal defense, to be consistent with constitutional principles, requires genuine, technically qualified opportunities for expression before the Public Administration.

In turn, Joneval Júnio Chaveiro³⁸ observes that the logic of adversarial proceedings within disciplinary administrative procedures presupposes a dialogical structure in which the administrative authority and the accused civil servant coexist under minimally equitable conditions. Although the decision-making power lies with the Administration, it must not position itself hierarchically above the accused within the adversarial structure, as such an imbalance would undermine the very essence of participation and defense. There is no effective adversarial process - nor a fair proceeding - when the civil servant's role is merely secondary and devoid of any real capacity to influence the outcome of the administrative decision.

Based on this understanding, the full exercise of the right of defense necessarily entails, as a fundamental prerogative, the assistance of legal counsel who possesses the technical and legal expertise to identify and articulate relevant procedural and substantive arguments. Legal representation, therefore, is not an expendable formality, but rather a structural component of adversarial proceedings, serving as a concrete safeguard for procedural balance and fairness within the framework of administrative sanctions.

Furthermore, the mandatory presence of legal counsel in disciplinary administrative proceedings finds its normative foundation in the Administrative Constitutional Due Process of Law, understood as the set of rights and fundamental guarantees enshrined in the 1988 Federal Constitution, particularly in Article 5, items LIV and LV³⁹. The observance of these guarantees is indispensable to the validity of the administrative sanctioning procedure, which must be conducted in accordance with constitutional standards that ensure the accused a real and effective opportunity for defense. As Ronaldo Brêtas de Carvalho Dias⁴⁰ emphasizes in his discussion on constitutional process within the Rule of Law, administrative proceedings must be regarded as instruments for the realization of these rights; thus, the failure to observe constitutional guarantees constitutes a defect capable of invalidating the administrative act.

It is important to note that the validity of the current binding precedent, which waives the mandatory presence of legal counsel for individuals under investigation in disciplinary administrative proceedings, constitutes a position that ought to be overcome - especially in light of the ongoing evolution and affirmation of fundamental rights. In this regard, Carolina Pereira Barreto *et al.* argue that "it is necessary to reconstruct the legal norm based on the new hierarchy of constitutional principles and to challenge the reasoning that a mere mechanical subsumption of the norm, which allows for the absence of legal representation in disciplinary administrative procedures, fulfills the substantive dimension of adversarial

³⁸ Chaveiro, Joneval Júnio. The Constitutional Principle of Adversarial Proceedings and Full Defense in Disciplinary Administrative Procedures. *Digital Journal of Administrative Law*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2015, p. 417. Available at: <http://www.revistas.usp.br/rdda/article/view/86875>. Accessed on: May 4, 2025.

³⁹ Brazil. [Constitution (1988)]. Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988. Brasília, DF: Office of the President of the Republic, [2016]. *Official Gazette of the Union*, Brasília, DF. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm. Accessed on: March 14, 2025.

⁴⁰ Brêtas, Ronaldo de Carvalho Dias. *Constitutional Procedure and the Rule of Law*. Belo Horizonte: Del Rey, 2022, p. 3.

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proceedings and full defense. Such a position amounts to a merely formal defense, devoid of the legal-technical substance required to persuade the adjudicator.”⁴¹

From this perspective, legal counsel in Disciplinary Administrative Proceedings emerges as an indispensable requirement under the constitutional principles of adversarial proceedings and full defense, despite Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme Court having removed the obligation of legal representation in such cases. This jurisprudential position is misaligned with the constitutional provisions enshrined in Article 5, items LIV and LV, of the 1988 Federal Constitution⁴² - particularly in view of the historical development of fundamental rights and their effective protection under a rights-based (guarantee-oriented) interpretation.

Given the punitive nature of Disciplinary Administrative Proceedings and their potential to restrict fundamental rights, strict observance of procedural guarantees is required. In this light, the absence of legal counsel undermines the effectiveness of full defense by limiting the accused’s capacity to mount a comprehensive, technically grounded defense. Accordingly, the mandatory presence of legal counsel in disciplinary procedures represents an inalienable expression of substantive due process of law, which demands a fair, balanced procedure capable of ensuring the maximum protection of the defendant’s rights.

Final remarks

This research set out to examine the compatibility of Administrative Disciplinary Proceedings (PAD) with the fundamental rights to adversarial proceedings and full legal defense, particularly in light of the due process of law as enshrined in the 1988 Federal Constitution of Brazil. The core research question focused on whether the absence of mandatory legal counsel, as permitted by Binding Precedent No. 5 of the Federal Supreme Court (STF), undermines the effectiveness of the constitutional guarantees that should govern disciplinary administrative proceedings. The hypothesis was that such absence constitutes a substantive limitation to the full realization of the rights to adversarial proceedings and full defense within the scope of public administration.

This hypothesis was confirmed through the application of the hypothetical-deductive method, which allowed for a structured analysis of constitutional provisions, doctrinal perspectives, and case law. The methodological procedures included bibliographic research, documentary analysis, and the review of relevant judicial precedents, with special attention to landmark decisions of the Federal Supreme Court and the Superior Court of Justice (STJ).

The findings demonstrate that although PADs are embedded within the State’s disciplinary authority, their punitive nature demands that they be conducted in strict compliance with constitutional parameters of legality, impartiality, and adversarial proceedings. The lack of mandatory legal counsel compromises these basic requirements of procedural justice, insofar as it deprives the defendant of professional representation capable of properly managing procedural and substantive legal defenses. It was observed that the constitutional provision guaranteeing adversarial proceedings and full legal defense (Article 5, items LIV and LV of the 1988 Federal Constitution) applies equally to both judicial and administrative spheres, and must therefore be observed in all phases of disciplinary administrative proceedings.

⁴¹ Barreto, Carolina Pereira *et al.* *The principle of adversarial proceedings and full defense in administrative disciplinary proceedings.* 2013, p. 128. Available at: <http://ri.ufs.br/jspui/handle/123456789/4357>. Accessed on: April 29, 2025.

⁴² Brazil. [Constitution (1988)]. Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988. Brasília, DF: Office of the President of the Republic, [2016]. *Official Gazette of the Union*, Brasília, DF. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm. Accessed on: March 14, 2025.

Given the confirmation of the research hypothesis, a critical reassessment of the interpretation given to Binding Precedent No. 5 becomes necessary considering the constitutional principles that inform the rule of law. The interpretation that reduces the requirement of legal counsel in PADs to a mere procedural option not only weakens the effectiveness of procedural guarantees but also fosters administrative practices that violate the balance between the parties and the legitimacy of disciplinary decisions. Reinterpreting this precedent through a constitutional hermeneutic committed to the effectiveness of fundamental rights is a pressing requirement of the rights-based model of constitutionalism, which admits no regression in the protection of individual liberties.

In other words, the continued validity of Binding Precedent No. 5, as currently formulated, constitutes an obstacle to the full effectiveness of fundamental rights and to the material realization of adversarial proceedings, as it undermines the equality of arms and reduces the right to legal defense to a formal gesture devoid of substantive legal effect. The revision of this understanding must consider the punitive character of PADs, the fundamental legal interests at stake, and the need to align administrative procedures with the same protective standards applicable to criminal proceedings. It is, therefore, a matter of constitutional coherence, which imposes upon the Federal Supreme Court and the legislature the duty to re-evaluate the scope of procedural guarantees within the public administration, so as to avoid interpretations that, although formally valid, depart from the meaning and purpose of fundamental rights as entrenched clauses of the Brazilian constitutional order.

In sum, legal counsel must be regarded not as an ancillary element of the proceedings, but as a structural condition of disciplinary administrative procedures and a prerequisite for achieving both procedural and substantive justice. Without legal counsel, the right to adversarial proceedings and full defense becomes illusory, and the administrative process risks diverging from the values that underpin the constitutional rule of law compact. The overcoming of Binding Precedent No. 5, therefore, is not merely a technical matter but an ethical and constitutional imperative - a commitment to the dignity of the defendant and to the Rule of Law.

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